

Caretraders

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INTRODUCTION

At Caretraders, we believe everybody should have access to being part of the solution to the problem of climate change. Our products will serve the almost 300 million Europeans who are concerned about climate change, yet have only few climate friendly consumption options. By enabling businesses to compete for customers with their green profiles, we can shift the cost of going green from consumers to businesses and thereby overcome one of the great barriers to a greener economy. We are currently launching a climate certification for clothing retailers and developing our platform for lean and rapid scaling to further market segments and geographical regions.

THEORY

Our main hypothesis is that consumers will prefer a climate friendly product to an identical but not climate friendly product sold at the same price. Our second hypothesis is that retailers can and want to increase their market share by using the appeal of climate friendliness. If these hypotheses hold true, we can serve both needs by facilitating a transparent offsetting procedure and certification for retailers.

METHODS

When a young mother enters a clothing store in Aarhus next month, the selection of dresses will be unchanged, but with one small addition: a voucher attached to each dress. The voucher gives her a small code for Caretraders.dk to verify that the storeowner has offset the exact dress she is holding in her hands. The mother will be satisfied by taking responsibility for the Earth she passes on to her children and the store owner will be proud to serve that intention before her competitors.

The European Union currently requires major industry to purchase one emission allowance for each ton of CO₂ they emit during a given year from a limited pool of allowances. In daily auctions, the industry asks to buy between two and five times more allowances than are auctioned off, so by purchasing these allowances we can effectively force the industry to reduce emissions. Since the CO₂ reductions are automatically distributed upon the entire industry, we get the cheapest CO₂ reductions possible, with the reliability of a major transparent legal framework.

CONCLUSION

By decentralizing the decision to be climate friendly across many people, geographies and sectors of the business-to-consumer markets, we can attain considerable CO₂ reductions.